
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES AND PERFORMANCE OF PHARMACEUTICAL FIRMS IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study examined relationship between product development strategies and performance of pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria. Specific objectives include to: Determine the extent of relationship between new product size and profitability and examine the extent of relationship between new product quality and sales volume of pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria. A survey research design was used. Total population of the study was one thousand eight hundred and ten (1, 810) marketing/production staff and major distributors. Sample size was three hundred and fifteen (315). The sampling technique used was convenience sampling technique while structured questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. It was found that new product size had significant positive relationship with profitability in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria and new product quality had significant positive relationship with sales volume in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study concluded that new product size and new product quality had significant positive relationship with performance of pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria. The study recommends that management should adhere and give priority to the new product size and new product quality of product content that can easily be observed; and also give it a good colour that can attract rather than repulse on sighting.

Keywords: Product Development Strategies, Performance, New Product Size, Product Quality, Profitability, Sales Volume.

INTRODUCTION

Prior to the inception of drug development and its manufacturing in the 1960s, pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria were based on large-scale importation of pharmaceuticals. The journey to drug development and manufacturing started in Nigeria with May & Baker Nigeria Plc which was founded in 1944 as Nigeria's first pharmaceutical company. Presently, some of these companies manufacture various pharmaceutical dosage forms cutting across various therapeutic classes such as analgesics, antimalarials, antibiotics, antiretrovirals, antacids, haematinics, vitamins and minerals, cough and cold remedies, anti-diarrhoea, antihistamines anti-ulcer, antihypertensive, antidiabetics etc. These products are widely and readily available in registered hospitals, pharmacies and distribution outlets nationwide (Yanelle, 2015).

Product development (PD) is, for every technology driven company, an important business process to secure future growth and sustained success in the marketplace. In today's changing business environment characterized by technological advances, intensified global competition, as well as changing customers and needs (Goffin &

Mitchell, 2015), the need for a successful product development is greater than ever. Product development is a process and like any other management process, it can be improved to achieve better results (McGrath, 2014). Unfortunately, while the academic literature has made numerous contributions to the understanding of how product development should work, less attention has been paid to the question of why organizations so often fail to execute their product development processes as desired (Repenning, 2016).

From the marketing standpoint, the socio-economic justification for the existence of any business organization is the satisfaction of customers' needs and wants. The organizational survival over-time depends on its ability to create loyal customers because its products match the needs of the buyers (Goedhuys & Veugelers, 2018). Thus, the organization meets its basic responsibility to the society through its product offerings. For a firm to compete effectively in the dynamic and competitive business environment and achieve set goals in terms of profitability, high sales volume, and large market share, it must continuously develop products and product lines to satisfy the constantly changing desires and needs of customers (Grundiche, 2014).

These Organizational adjustments in response to new customer preferences even make it necessary to modify existing products, introduce new ones or eliminate products that are unsuccessful. Product development is a broad field of endeavour dealing with design, creation and marketing of new product, (Yanelle, 2015). It encompasses product planning as well the technical activities of product research, engineering design, etc to take advantage of potential opportunities facing a company's product idea in a market.

Product development is very critical to organizational performance because the product is the cornerstone of the firm's marketing mix: every other element rests on the product. Product is not used to mean only tangible 'things', but includes services (the intangibles) as well as things that can be touched and seen and tasted. This explains why Kotler (2014) sees it as a bundle of physical, service, and symbolic particulars expected to yield satisfaction or benefits to the buyer. Product is the most visible contact a firm has with buyers. Product is a fundamental tool of marketing because it carries with its benefits or utilities sought by the buyer. A product becomes ordinary bolts and nuts if it does not provide the needs or solutions to buyers' problems. If this is true, the buyer, therefore, pays for the benefits, utilities, solutions and needs the product provides Haeussler, *et al* (2012). Thus, a passenger pays for transportation to solve mobility needs, a student pays school fees to obtain knowledge or education, a bank customer pays bank charges for safekeeping of cash and other valuables as well as other bank services while a hotel customer pays to obtain accommodation, relaxation and leisure.

Product is the heart sustenance of organizational performance because a firm's first task is to produce and sell to large extent. Product development designs determine what prices can be charged, what forms of marketing promotion or communications are needed, what distribution channels are used, the nature of people or service personnel used, delivery process that can satisfy customers (Ejionueme & Nebo, 2021). In a study of 721 U.K. manufacturing firms during the period 1972–1983, for instance, Geroski *et al.*, (2013) showed that the number of innovations produced by firms had a positive effect on their operating profit margin. Clark and Fujimoto (2019) performance in a development project is determined by a firm's product strategy and by its capabilities in overall process and organization. They further claim that firms' products help to shape the market environment; the nature of the market environment changes as consumers and competitors learn from new products and services. Goedhuys and Veugelers (2018) found that innovative performance is an important

driver for firm growth in particular the combination of product and process innovations that significantly improves firm growth. Financial markets may be attuned sharply to product development outcomes in publicly traded firms (Anurag and Nelson, 2014).

Since the purpose of product development is to provide satisfaction for customers and to face competitive threat, every marketing organization such as the pharmaceutical firms is in a highly dynamic situation Sharma and Lacey, (2014). This is because customers' needs are constantly changing. Their incomes, lifestyles, level of education, sophistication and technology are dynamic and not static. Therefore, their marketing policies have been dynamic, not static, and the products offered to the market have come constantly under review and frequent changes. Market analysis has shown that many breweries in Nigeria have introduced many innovations in their product development strategy (Etuk, 2013). Products are packaged in big and small bottles, cans with many lines and depth.

Statement of the Problem

As pointed out in the background of the study, one of the single most important activity of any firm, whether service or manufacturing organization, is the development of a new product that meets the needs of certain groups of consumers. Product innovations has been linked to organizational performance in terms of profit, market share, sales volume, net return on investment, customer loyalty and satisfaction (Geroski *et al*, 2013). This is why smart organizations spend their money, time, efforts and other resources in researching and developing new products (Allen & Hamilton, 2017). For instance, research shows that U.S companies have increased the amount spent on new products research by 17 percent per year and they spent \$600 billion in research and development of new products (Allen & Hamilton, 2017).

Although new product contributes significantly to organizational performance, studies have equally shown that large percentage of new products fail both in developed and developing countries like Nigeria. And this does not contribute to the well-being of any organization. For instance, in U.S Booz, Allein and Hamilton (2017) reported in their studies that out of every seven ideas that enter the product process, only one emerges as a commercial success. They further discovered that 46 percent of the total funds spent on new products by U.S industry goes for products that fail or abandoned. Similarly, Crowford (2015) estimated that 40 to 45 percent of marketed new products fail while Hopkin (2014) reported that about 40 percent of industrial new products fail in the market place.

The situation is the same in Nigerian pharmaceutical industry. Mba (2015) reported that the era of 1985-2010 in Nigeria has heralded the regime of pharmaceutical products failures ranging from analgesics, antimalaria, anti-histamins, anti-ulcer, anti-diabetic and anti-hypertensive drugs. Studies have also shown that there may be more poor quality, fake and sub-standard drugs than genuine one in circulation (Osibo, 2018). Even more worrisome is the fact that the effect of these poor quality sub-standard pharmaceutical products go unnoticed most of the time except in cases where it results in mass death (Osibo, 2018).

The scenario above shows that the argument about whether or not new product development strategies contributes to organizational performance is polarized into two. As evident from previous studies, some school of thought believe new product development and innovations contributes to organizational performance whereas others believe that substantial percentage of new products fail and this means a waste of organizational

resources. Based on these schools of thought, the research result on this subject is inconclusive, thus permitting room for further investigation. Based on this inconclusive research result, managers face the dilemma of whether or not to continue spending money on new product development or deploy resources to other more meaningful strategies that will achieve organizational objectives. As a result of this, there is the need for the researcher to further ascertain the relationship between product development strategies and organizational performance especially in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria, where evidence from previous studies is scarce.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the relationship between product development strategies and organizational performance in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria. Other specific objectives include to:

- i. Determine the extent of relationship between new product size and profitability in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.
- ii. Examine the extent of relationship between new product quality and sales volume in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Product Development Strategies

Marketing scholars have offered definitions of a product from different perspectives but most seem to agree that a product is something a buyer acquires or purchases to satisfy personal or business (organizational commercial or government) needs. Most scholars also agree that product is the most important of the marketing mix (Nebo, 2019; Ejionueme, 2018). Product development has been defined as the focus on the needs of the current customers and the wider customer markets (Ansoff, 1987). Kotler (2000) says in product development a firm remains in its present markets but develops new products for these markets.

Product Size

Product Size is the organization's magnitude as reflected in the number of productions in the organization. Product size has often been described as an important variable that influences structural design. Product size (as defined by the number of product) has received substantial attention from researchers and management writers as a fundamental component affecting organizational design, structure and shape. Some researchers claim size influences organizational effectiveness and efficiency and some claim it does not. Of the various structural variables, size is perhaps the one most likely to be associated with other organizational characteristics (Hofler, 2010).

Product Quality

The definition of product quality by (Trentin *et al.*, 2012) is the ability of a product to perform its function; it includes the products of overall durability, reliability, precision, ease of operational repair and other valued attributes. Product quality is the ability of a product to perform its function.

Organizational Performance

Performance is central to success in today's fast moving competitive markets, and measuring organizational performance is critical to managing it effectively. Performance is a measure of how efficiently and effectively managers use, available resources to satisfy customer and achieve organizational goals (Trentin *et al.*, 2012).

Profitability

Profitability is the ability of a business to earn a profit. A profit is what is left of the revenue a business generates after it pays all expenses directly related to the generation of the revenue, such as producing a product, and other expenses related to the conduct of the business' activities (Grimsley, 2015). Profitability at microeconomic level has been studied depending also on indicators such as current ratio, liquid ratio, receivables turnover ratio and working capital to total asset (Singh & Pandey, 2018).

Sales Volume

Sales volume is a measure of growth embedded in the adoption of a particular organizational performance adopted by a firm, expressed in unit or quantity of what is sold. A company's ability or its managerial power is expressed by sales volume. According to Marquis (2015), the strength of a company is expressed in sales volume among other parameters.

Theoretical Framework

Products Development Theory

This paper was anchored on products development theory. It was developed by Lancaster in (2017). Products satisfy relatively few simple needs such as food, shelter, and entertainment. These products are produced through the production of various goods and services. Thus, basic human needs can be satisfied through many combinations of materials and technologies that resulted needs for production. Many goods produced in an advanced economy meet similar needs; consumers apparently select only a few products on the basis of their price and different qualities or features. The traditional analysis of consumer demand deals with consumer choice under budget constraints in which preference ordering is used to maximize utility when price changes.

Empirical Review

Ling (2018) confirmed the effects of product quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in Malaysia. The purpose of the research was to study the factors that can assist a company to build a sustainable competitive advantage through the effective enhancement of customer satisfaction and ultimately customer loyalty. Garvin's eight dimensions of product quality in performance, features, reliability, conformance, durability, serviceability, aesthetics and perceived quality are dimensions of product quality that affect customer satisfaction which impacts loyalty. The results provide insights to understand the dimensions of product quality that affect customer satisfaction and higher satisfaction leads to higher customer loyalty in the engineering industry in Malaysia.

Wiwiek, Daryanto and Maharani (2021) examined profitability ratio analysis before and during covid-19 in Indonesia. This study aimed to analyze the difference in the financial performance of PT. Japfa Comfeed Indonesia before and during the COVID-19 pandemic which is between the years 2019 to 2020. This study focused on profitability ratios that include return on assets, return on invested capital, return on equity, gross margin percentage, and profit margin as a part of the financial performance of the company.

Bianda and Mardawiyah (2021) conducted study on Profitability ratio analysis as measurement tool of financial performance study case of pt Pertamina on Kenya. The company's financial performance results have increased and decreased, and the company should know how the company's performance is to stabilize its operational state. This research method uses secondary data to acquire financial reports for the period 2015-2019, and with descriptive analysis. From the results that have been processed by researchers, PT Pertamina (Persero) has not been maximized in calculating the profitability ratio because the results are still below the average industry ratio.

Saeed, and Khashayar (2021) examined understanding sales volume antecedents: measuring the role of consumer-oriented selling and sales promotion in Iran. The results of structural equation analysis by LISREL were utilized to test the proposed hypotheses in this study. The result shows that all sales promotion dimensions are independently and jointly predict sales volume. This implies that coupon, premiums, bonus, free samples and price promotion have significant effect on sales volume.

Ndem and Ezekiel (2019) conducted the impact of trade promotion on sales volume in the beer industry in Nigeria. This study was on trade promotion and its impact on sales growth of the Guinness Plc Nigeria. A survey research design was applied in the course of the study, with a well-designed questionnaire on the subject matter. A simple random sampling technique was used for sample selection. The analysis of 36 questionnaires from wholesaler and retailer of Guinness product, with a simple regression model on statistical package for social science (SPSS) indicated that sales contest, special allowance, and buying allowance impact on sales volume of Guinness products but with varying strength of prediction.

Gaps in Empirical Review

Many extant literatures were reviewed in order to address issue of product development strategies and organizational performance of pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria. Meanwhile there was a lot of inconsistent of findings over other authors' works, many of them were carried out in developed countries with different sector of the economy. Dirisu, Oluwole and Ibidunni (2013, Mbithi, Muturi and Rambo (2015), Junfeng, Benedetto and Hoenig (2021), This paper aim was to review the organizational performance definition and measurement perspectives. The main research question under investigation was what the concept of organizational performance measurement. Based on issue of product development strategies and organizational performance, the current study remains most current as at 2024. This is gapping the study covered.

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative descriptive research design was utilized for this study. Descriptive research describes characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. Primary sources were used for the study and these were sourced from the questionnaire distributed to all the distributors, production and marketing staff of the pharmaceutical companies selected for the study. The target population of the study consists of all the major distributors, production and marketing staff of the five pharmaceutical companies used for study. Total number of marketing and production staff is 1,503 while major distributors are 307. The sample size was 315 using Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula. For this study, convenience sampling techniques were used in selecting the distributors and staff that constitute the sample size.

The instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into sections A and B. Section A is designed to gather demographic data of the respondents like gender, educational qualification, age, and work experience while section B contained twenty (20) questions designed to gather data relating to the research questions. The constructs of the independent variables (product size, product quality, product taste and product packaging) and organizational performance variables (profitability, sales volume, market share and customer loyalty) were got from the extant literature (Nwokah, Ugoji and Ofoegbu, 2009). In responding to the questionnaire, respondents were required to indicate the extent to which answer options describe their opinion on the variables under investigation. The questions were designed in 5-points likert scale ranging from 5-strongly agree (SA) to 1-strongly disagree (SD).

About three (3) postgraduate research assistants were employed by the researcher, they were fully trained and educated for the purpose of the study. Then it took them one month to administered questionnaire and collects them back. The face validity of the research instrument was used and determined by the supervisor. After that some copies issued to the potential respondents to complete. The essence is to eliminate some phrases that are ambiguous or may be misinterpreted. Corrections from the researcher’s supervisor and the potential respondent effected before using it to check the reliability of the questionnaire.

In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted by issuing 20 copies of the validated questionnaire to potential respondents in Enugu State. Their responses on the instrument used to determine its reliability using Cronbach Alpha (α) Reliability test for internal consistency of the instrument with a threshold of 0.70. as determined by Nunnally and Berstein (1994). Methods of Data analysis consist of descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency and tables were used in presenting and analyzing the data while in inferential statistics, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) model was utilized in testing the formulated hypotheses.

Test of Hypothesis One

Statement of the Hypothesis One

H₀₁: New product size has no significant positive relationship with profitability in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

H_{a1}: New product size has significant positive relationship with profitability in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the sign of the coefficient is negative and probability value >0.05 . Otherwise, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate accordingly.

Correlation Matrix Analysis

		New Product Size	Profitability
New Product Size	Pearson Correlation	1	.939**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	450	450
Profitability	Pearson Correlation	.939**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

	N	450	450
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 0.25

From the correlation result shown above, we have new product size and profitability in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria with a probability value of .000 and $r = .939$ which indicates that there was significant positive relationship between new product size and profitability in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

Decision for Hypothesis One

Given the probability value of .000 is less than 0.05 level of significant and coefficient value of .939. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate concluding that new product size had significant positive relationship with profitability in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Statement of the Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant positive relationship between new product quality and sales volume in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

H_{a2}: There is significant positive relationship between new product quality and sales volume in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the sign of the coefficient is negative and probability value > 0.05 . Otherwise, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate accordingly.

Correlation Matrix Analysis

Correlations			
		New Product Quality	Sales Volume
New Product Quality	Pearson Correlation	1	.839**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	450	450
Sales Volume	Pearson Correlation	.839**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	450	450
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Extracted from SPSS Version 0.25

From the correlation result shown above, we have new product quality and sales volume in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria with a probability value of .000 and $r = .839$ which indicates that there was significant positive relationship between new product quality and sales volume in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

Decision for Hypothesis Two

Evidence given probability value of .000 is less than 0.05 level of significant and coefficient value of .839. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate concluding that new product quality had significant positive relationship with sales volume in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

After data analysis, the following major findings shows that:

1. New product size had significant positive relationship with profitability in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.
2. New product quality had significant positive relationship with sales volume in pharmaceutical firms in South East, Nigeria.

Conclusion

Based on findings we concluded that new product development strategies especially new product size and product quality influence profitability, sales volume respectively in pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on findings of this study:

1. Production of various product sizes should be encouraged to allow customers have the opportunity to make a choice based on their income and comfort to take the pills as prescribed by doctors.
2. Pharmaceutical companies should carefully choose product quality that are capable of attracting customers' interests and improving sales volume of pharmaceutical firms.

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